

The traditional media in Ethiopia according to the income level can be considered radio and television access. The television access is for middle and high income level of people which are mostly found in the urban area of the countries. Whereas the low income level of the society is using radio as source of traditional media. On the other hand according to the level of education the traditional media for the educated people is optional of having reading newspaper and magazine whereas the illiterate segment of the society is still in the darkness of having reading source of traditional media. On the other hand the urban area of the society have multiple option of using newspaper, magazine, radio or Television as source of traditional media. the rural location has not yet have a electric access and the option of wind and solar energy is limited for the high-income people thus the mass of the rural area has the position of using radio as source of traditional media still. The race/ethnicity have role in Ethiopian traditional media where Amharic language speaking citizen have more option of choice among the media where the others have limited access and options. The internet penetration and accessibility let start from Ethiopia's population Ethiopia had a population of 116.4 million in January 2021 Ethiopia's. population increased by 2.9 million (+2.5%) between January 2020 and January 2021. 50.0% of Ethiopia's population is female, while 50.0% of its population is male [note: the United Nations does not publish data for genders other than 'female' and 'male']. 21.9% of Ethiopia's population lives in urban centers, while 78.1% lives in rural areas. There were 23.96 million internet users in Ethiopia in January 2021. The number of internet users in Ethiopia increased by 2.8 million (+13%) between 2020 and 2021. Internet penetration in Ethiopia stood at 20.6% in January 2021. There were 6.70 million social media users in Ethiopia in January 2021. The number of social media users in Ethiopia increased by 500 thousand (+8.1%) between 2020 and 2021. The number of social media users in Ethiopia was equivalent to 5.8% of the total population in January 2021. There were 44.86 million mobile connections in Ethiopia in January 2021. The number of mobile connections in Ethiopia increased by 710 thousand (+1.6%) between January 2020 and January 2021. The number of mobile connections in Ethiopia in January 2021 was equivalent to 38.5% of the total population. ^[1]

Ethiopians were denied more than a single state television broadcaster for over five decades. Broadcast media has been under the tighter grip of the government until recently.

When the government finally decided to loosen its grip, it invited political allies first, even though 40 companies applied for licenses. Even among those they trusted, they licensed only a few closely vetted groups and individuals known for their compliance and affiliation to the ruling party. Up until October 2016, nine TV companies which echoed the state propaganda machine, but with regional name and representation, have been in operation. Since, EBA has licensed three others: Fana Broadcasting, Walta Information Center, and Dimtse Weyane. Companies affiliated with EPRDF parties own all three. Local news on the state and pro-government media is full of developmental stories about the progress of the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam or road and housing projects. There are also dozens of community radios and regional FM stations up and running. But their number by no means guarantees a diversity of voices. There are also TV stations with second-country license, like Kana, Nahu, JTV, LTV, Ethiopian Broadcasting Service (EBS), and Ethiopian News Network (ENN). But they do not discuss politics and, if they did, the government might close their representative office in the Addis, and revoke their agents' licenses. Since illiteracy is still common, radio is as key source of information for people both in cities and rural areas. It's partly for this reason that the print press enjoys more freedom than radio. The availability of mobile phones with FM receivers has dramatically increased listenership and therefore government concern. One of the most popular radio stations is the privately owned Sheger FM, which is also broadcast online. However, there is not much political news, so many Ethiopians still tune their shortwaves into international stations like the Voice of America's Amharic, Affan Oromo and Tigrigna services; and the Deutsche Welle Amharic service from Bonn. The new entrant is BBC radio in the three languages mentioned above.^[2]

The people of Wollega province in the western part of Ethiopia did not have access to the internet from January 2020 until now where sometimes comes and goes again. The internet and telecommunications blackout was connected to an ongoing security crackdown in the area which has seen conflict between government forces and rebels. The chief executive officer of internet provider Ethio-Telecom said that the shutdown was a result of insecurity in the province. She apologized for the disruptions and said that the company would defer to the decision of the authorities, who have now announced a reconnection in western Oromia—that is, in Kelem, west and east Wollega, and Horo Guduru Wollega. In this case

the only option they have is the radio and television where television is found on the urban area. ^[3]

When we look in the digital election messaging and its feasibility Digital media in Ethiopia is in its infancy. The connection is slow and frequent power cuts contribute to the unavailability of connection from time to time, even in the capital. The Internet is monopolized by the state owned Ethio Telecom. The government considers telecoms a cash cow and that, coupled with its ability to control the flow of information, means there is no way they will open it up for market competition in the foreseeable future. It is expensive and sometimes a luxury for the majority in small towns to use Internet cafes. Instead many people tend to use their mobile data, which is relatively costly as well. People stand outside hotels or step into lobbies to download content for later use. There are no exact figures on what percentage of the population can access the Internet. However, mobile subscription is surging and is said to have reached 50 million people, which would be the largest in Africa, surpassing Nigeria. A lack of knowledge about how to record events, how to edit, and how to upload them have discouraged local media from active engagement. But some computer and digital media literate young people in cities are trying to take advantage by setting up websites and online video channels, like DireTube, to disseminate unverified texts, photos and videos. Amateurish channels, mostly content aggregators, are mushrooming, which has led to the dissemination of fake news. Unfortunately, there is a large segment of the population who believe whatever is posted on social media is true. This tendency, in the long-term, undoubtedly hurts the perception of online media. The unprecedented penetration of mobile telephones has played a great part in enabling people to access digital content. These devices are mostly imported from China and are available at a cheap price, which has led to a fast diffusion. Websites set-up by media savvy youth are too cautious to discuss politics as long as they are based in the country, even if there exists no legal framework that can license or regulate online media ownership. At its introduction, the Internet promised to free groups and individuals promoting democracy from threats and censorship. However, activists and politicians instead have been thrown into jail just for expressing their opinion on social media. But the Internet has also paved the way for citizen journalists. On balance, the Internet has probably advanced a culture of open discussion. Blogging, in its strict sense,

however, has not taken off and there are not many popular bloggers, ultimately, this is the era of the Internet. The state could block it for a time, but it will not dismantle it altogether.

For the above and more when we developing election message and communication for the public the format and the language we must consider is that peace campaigns in Ethiopia result from five inter-related factors: the ideal of orderly elections and potential to instrumentalism peace encourages a diverse range of actors to invest their time and energy in such campaigns; a fear that elections will descend into violence guarantees a responsive public; the difficulty of addressing the underlying drivers of violence encourages an individualization of responsibility; and donor funding helps to ensure the pervasiveness of peace campaigns. In this way, our analysis has underscored how peace campaigns have been so durable precisely because they have been driven both from within and from without, are communicated through multiple channels including religious leaders and the mass media, and resonate with the concerns of individual citizens as well as with the self-interest of politicians. There is much that is positive about this trend. Peace messaging appears to have contributed to lower levels of violence around elections. However, an emphasis on peace can be problematic, because it may strengthen the hand of authoritarian governments and so facilitate the emergence of a peace democracy, in which the fear of conflict is used to prioritize stability and order to the detriment of democracy. The power of this discourse and attendant insistence on peace and reconciliation lie, at least in part, in the vivid memories of violence and instability that exist in many countries, and in the difficulty of contesting these narratives. It is difficult and often dangerous for individuals to publicly set themselves against peace, reconciliation and order; or for their opposites: violence, division and disorder. As a result, pro-democracy activists and engaged academics have often struggled to challenge the emergence of peace democracy.

Significantly, most of the factors that we argue drive an emphasis on peace have been features of African politics for some time, and radical change seems unlikely any time soon. Given this, it is worrying that peace messaging has worked to silence dissent in countries, where democracy is already relatively weak. In these competitive-authoritarian states—of which there are many on the continent—the promise of peace is interwoven with the threat of repression. Under these conditions, peace campaigns become less likely to genuinely

resolve existing disputes and societal tensions, and more likely to store up further grievances and problems for the future. It is therefore imperative that academics, activists and domestic and international players re-think how best to promote peace without eroding democracy. And all those message must consider the majority of the ethnic language to be used as the way of convey it in both the internet and traditional media. [4]

To conclude the goal of strategic political communication during election campaigns is to use information and communication as strategically and effectively as possible to reach the objectives that have been set. And in the case of Ethiopia consultation with stakeholders starting form social media activites to the traditional media workers in the must. The strategic goals of parties and campaigns are thus imperative, which suggests that an understanding of strategic political communication during election campaigns requires an understanding of political parties and campaigns as organizations. For example, some parties are more vote-seeking, while others may be more policy-seeking. Such party characteristics will influence both the priority given to campaigning and campaign communication, and how the parties plan and run their campaigns. [5] At the same time, campaign practices and communication are always dynamic and shaped by the contextual conditions formed by the political system, the media system, laws and regulations, the political culture, and the type of parties and party competition. What works in one context may thus not work in another context. While there are cross-national patterns in campaign practices and campaign communication, more detailed analyses usually reveals country-differences beneath the surface. Hence, while it is important to identify macro trends, it is also important not to oversimplify. Last but not list the media mapping must also include for person with disabilities with hearing challenge and see on the way of reaching which are almost 17.1 % of the Society.

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